

Agent-Based Simulation and Process Mining for ESG-Aware Insurance Premium Modelling

Chaithra Jayanth

jchaithra@gmail.com

Abstract

Agent-Based Modeling and Process Mining are increasingly applied in the context of Business Process Management. This study aims to integrate Agent-Based Simulation and Process Mining to evaluate the dynamic relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors and insurance premium modeling. The study simulated insured companies as adaptive agents whose ESG investments impact their financial risk profiles and premiums. Using event logging and the PM4Py library, we mine and visualize behavioral patterns, offering insights into policy effectiveness and strategic decision-making. The results reveal that incentivizing green investments can significantly influence ESG improvements and reduce insurance premiums, thereby fostering sustainable behavior in the corporate ecosystem.

Keywords: ESG, Agent-Based Modeling, Process Mining, Insurance Premiums, Sustainability, Business Process Modeling

Introduction

In the contemporary world, achieving a sustainable business model is not a social obligation anymore; an organization's entire success is influenced by sustainability activities since they improve market access, growth prospects, and customer happiness (Achieving ESG Sustainability Goals with Process Mining-Based Transformation Program, 2021). According to (Achieving ESG Sustainability Goals with Process Mining-Based Transformation Program), seeking financial financing and preserving a company's reputation in the marketplace are now requirements (2021).

As global awareness of climate and social governance risks grows, insurers are factoring ESG performance into premium pricing. Nevertheless, the behavioral consequences of ESG - motivated incentives is difficult to appreciate. According to Carannante et al., “ESG exemplifies the practice of ethical leadership, pointing toward ethical conduct for environmental, social, and governance activities” (2024). Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) behaviors are rarely taken into consideration when pricing risk in traditional insurance models. ESG is becoming a crucial component of financial health and company sustainability, yet regulators and insurers lack useful tools to model and comprehend. The main research questions we are answering are: How organization’s ESG practices change over time, how corporate conduct may be impacted by regulatory incentives or penalties based on ESG performance and which choices result in better or worse ESG compliance? This paper introduces a new simulation-based framework that combines agent-based modelling and process mining to analyse the impacts of ESG thresholds on corporate behaviour and insurance rates.

Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) Models have gained significant interest in recent times in both research and industries (Sulis, 2023). “ABM is used to investigate heterogeneous insurer strategies for a market where premium is determined by the balance of supply and demand” (City Research Online - Agent-Based Modelling in the Insurance Industry: An Exploration of Emergent Systemic Risk, 2023). These models have been efficiently applied in various domains such as, health care, social problems and spatial impact (Sulis, 2023). In parallel, process mining has emerged as a powerful technique for uncovering patterns from event logs, enabling organizations to achieve transparency in workflows, identify bottlenecks, and uncover improvement opportunities at various stages of a process (Achieving ESG Sustainability Goals with Process Mining-Based Transformation Program, 2021). By combining ABS and process mining, this study leverages both behavioral modeling and trace-based analytics to simulate and explain how ESG-related decisions influence insurance dynamics.

Method

Simulation Framework

This paper builds an agent-based model to simulate ESG-prompted dynamics of insurance premium pricing. Using the Mesa framework (Mesa Documentation, 2025), the model simulates the interplay among ESG behavior, financial risk and regulatory incentives for 100 fictive insured companies over 50 time steps.

Agent Design

Each agent is associated with a company with the following attributes:

- An ESG score randomly sampled from a uniform distribution $[0.3, 0.9]$.

- A sampled financial risk level, for which the value is uniformly from $[0.1, 1.0]$ a dynamically determined insurance premium corresponding to the ESG score and the risk level.
- Agents receive a green action with a 40% probability at their disposal if their ESG score is lower than 0.6. One green investment adds 0.05 units to the ESG score. This affects how rates are much for their future.

Policy Simulation

We introduce threshold-based policy rules to mimic regulatory action:

- Agents with $ESG \geq 0.8$ discount 5% of the premium.
- $ESG \leq 0.4$ agents suffer a 10% premium penalty.

These interventions resemble the carbon-pricing mechanisms and green subsidies within regulatory systems and encouraging ESG behaviors by means of economic inducements.

Data Collection and Process Mining

All agent events (evaluations, investments, policy actions) are logged into structured event logs exported as CSV files. Process mining is conducted using PM4Py (PM4Py Documentation, 2025):

- Directly-Follows Graphs (DFGs): To identify dominant behavioral sequences.
- Alpha Miner: To reconstruct Petri nets, revealing underlying process structures.
- Trace Variant Analysis: To differentiate compliance and non-compliance pathways.

Analysis Techniques

- Descriptive Analysis of premiums and ESG scores over time.

- Process mining to uncover typical patterns of behaviors - challenges to invest before rewarded.
- Trace variant analysis to examine compliance and non-compliance patterns.

This multi-method approach enables both behavioral analysis and process discovery, forming the basis for future predictive modeling.

Results

Simulation results demonstrate progressive ESG improvements among agents and corresponding premium reductions. DFGs highlight frequent sequences such as investment actions preceding premium discounts. Petri nets visualize the overall ESG compliance process, showing loops of investment and evaluation. Variant analysis reveals distinct behavioral clusters: proactive ESG investors benefiting from discounts and laggards incurring penalties.

Outcome 1

According to the simulation's results, the average insurance premium stayed constant at about 1205.60 units, and the average ESG score stabilized at 0.691 by steps 45 to 49. This implies that the population of corporate agents achieved behavioral equilibrium following a sequence of green investments and regulatory policy applications.

The "ESG Score vs. Premium over Time" line graph graphically illustrates the inverse relationship between premiums and ESG scores, with increasing ESG scores linked to a slow decline in premiums. This illustrates how well the reward-penalty policy thresholds that were

added to the simulation worked

Fig.1: Graph depicting “ESG score vs Premium over Time”.

Outcome 2

Particularly among agents with initially low ESG ratings, process mining approaches, such as Directly-Follows Graphs (DFGs), revealed similar patterns including consecutive ESG evaluations followed by green investments. A Petri net model was rebuilt by the Alpha Miner, exposing the general framework of agent decision-making.

The dominance of the ESG evaluation phase (5000 occurrences) and its frequent shift to green investment actions (152 cases), rewards (600 cases), or penalties (23 cases) are highlighted in a comprehensive DFG graphic. It also provides subtle insights into the dynamics of ESG behavior by displaying uncommon but illuminating routes, such as agents investing and still being penalized or cycling between rewards and penalties. The circular routes between

investment, reward, and reevaluation show successful ESG improvement cycles, while the strong self-loop on evaluation indicates conservative behavior unless driven by regulation or risk exposure.

Fig.2: Directly-Follows Graph depicting ESG Decision Events

Discussion

Abdelaziz et al., in their 2011 work, state that “Decarbonisation in industry can be achieved through energy saving technologies, fuel switching, management approaches, imposition of standards, fiscal policies and agreements on specific energy targets” (Budinis et al., 2020). Sustainability-driven economic models increasingly emphasize the role of ESG metrics in financial services. Katsamakos & Sanchez-Cartas suggests that ESG investment is used for process or product innovation, in addition to attracting consumers as competition is unaffected (2023). Insurance companies are particularly well-positioned to integrate ESG data into risk assessment and pricing mechanisms. However, understanding the dynamic interaction between ESG performance and financial risk over time remains a complex challenge. This study presents

an agent-based simulation model coupled with process mining techniques to analyze how ESG behaviors of companies influence insurance premium structures.

The integration of ABM and process mining provides a dual perspective: quantitative outcomes and qualitative process insights. This enables insurers and regulators to understand not only how premiums evolve but also the behavioral pathways leading to ESG compliance or non-compliance. The findings suggest that threshold-based incentives effectively motivate green investments, but also highlight potential policy refinements to target lagging agents.

Based on their financial risk and ESG scores, firm agents use the virtual environment created by this article to decide which green investments to undertake. It helps insurers comprehend the behavioral ramifications of ESG-based incentives by simulating how ESG behavior affects insurance premium pricing.

It also acts as a trial ground for policy initiatives. Before putting these policies into practice, the model assesses whether they successfully promote ESG improvements by establishing thresholds that result in rewards or penalties.

Furthermore, decision-making pathways are transparent when process mining tools are applied to the simulation's event logs (KPMG, 2019). This method provides a deeper understanding than aggregate results by exposing sequences of behaviors that result in ESG improvement or degradation, such as investing before receiving incentives.

Lastly, the work in this paper establishes the foundation for combining machine learning with real-world ESG statistics. Future uses of the model could include forecasting default risk for low-ESG companies, creating the best green incentive schemes, and creating flexible premium pricing schemes that incentivize sustainable practices.

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